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 Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters in The Same Cell

DELIVERABLE D4.1

REPORT OF THE RESULTS OF CALIBRATION METHODOLOGY

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Introduction

WP4 focus, among other aspects, on assays to test and validate the prototypes to measure various biophysical parameters of living cells. This deliverable explains this validation work carried out during this first part of the project.

Initially, we planned to use non-biological samples to measure mechanical properties with two different techniques. Later, we have improved this plan, changing to use fixed suspended cells, with properties closer to the living cells we aim to characterize with the prototypes developed in this project. Following this rationale, we have tested fixed ARPE19 cells by the micropipette aspiration technique, as reference, and by the microfluidics devices developed in this project. In this report we describe the experiments and the results obtained by the two procedures.

1.1 Scope and justification

In this project we have been able to design novel microfluidics techniques for mechanical and electrical characterization of cells. Microfluidic devices are a type of system known as LODs (Lab-on-a-Chip). They are miniaturized systems—on the order of micrometers—with various geometries. Their purpose is to manipulate small fluid volumes operating under laminar flow conditions. Those used for cDC (cell deformation characterization) include channels with micrometric constrictions through which cells are made to pass.

In previous works, we had developed a technology for producing microfluidics devices with various channels with constrictions and for assessing mechanical parameters of suspended cells passing through the constrictions of the device. In this project, we aim to extend the possibilities of microfabricated devices to measure a variety of biophysical properties. Initially, during the first part of the project we have developed the technology for the mechanical and electrical characterization of single cells.

To assess both mechanical parameters and electrical parameters, a model to interpret the direct observations and measurements is required. In the case of the mechanical parameters, object of this report, developing an adequate model is critical to obtain measurements for single cells ^[1]. Otherwise, simplistic models allow only assessing mechanical parameters for a whole population of cells ^[2,3]. The model developed previously has been adapted to the new devices, allowing us to obtain three mechanical parameters for each cell.

1.2 Objectives of this deliverable

The main goal of Deliverable D4.1 is to present the outcomes related to using the developed biophysical characterization techniques and comparison of the results with those obtained by using other techniques.

Specifically, this deliverable seeks to:

- O1. Validate the procedure to measure mechanical parameters with the microfluidics devices.
- O2. Obtain mechanical properties of fixed cells with the microfluidics devices.

- O3. Obtain mechanical properties of fixed cells by micropipette aspiration.
- O4. Compare the results obtained with the two techniques.

These objectives contribute to the broader aim of WP4, which is essentially to validate our prototypes and procedures for biophysical characterization of cells.

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Microfluidics devices used in this study

2.1 Design of the microfluidics devices with microchannels containing constrictions

The devices designed in this project are structured with several microchannels, each having an inlet and, at the opposite end, an outlet for the fluid, usually arranged symmetrically. Between these ends, the microchannel can take on different geometries. In our case, they feature one or more constrictions, and may also include secondary structures, such as a filter between the inlet and the constriction, designed to block large particles or cells that could otherwise obstruct the channel.

Several designs have been previously with various configurations, varying both in the number of constrictions and in the width of the constriction. In this project, we decided to use devices with 1, 3, or 12 constrictions in parallel microchannels connected to the same inlet and outlet. For this analysis, comparing experimental techniques with two different techniques, we have used devices with one single microchannel and one single constriction. The single-constriction channel is designed as shown in the following picture.

Figure 1. Design of a channel of a microfluidic device with a single constriction. The units are in micrometers (μm).

The device in Figure 1 has a constriction width of 5 μm . We designed and fabricated also devices with 7.5 and 10 μm , so that suspended cells with various size ranges can be tested, with heights of 20, 30 and 40 μm , respectively.

2.2 Production of the devices

To produce the devices with channels as described in the previous section, we designed molds to produce devices containing 11 channels. Moreover, the devices are arranged within the same mold so that several of them can fit together, with “+”-shaped marks indicating where to cut. Silicon wafers are used to fabricate these molds through photolithography. The molds were manufactured at the CNRS in France, and their appearance can be seen in Figure 2. In the mold shown in Figure 2, a total of six microfluidic devices can be observed on the same wafer, including single-constriction devices and twelve-constriction devices.

To fabricate the microfluidic devices using the mold, the following materials were used: a base and a curing agent that acts as a catalyst for the former (both from the Sylgard® 184 Silicone Elastomer kit) to produce a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) sheet, which forms the main material of the device, as well as a Petri dish, aluminum foil, and a microscope slide. In addition, certain laboratory equipment is needed to carry out this process.

Figure 2. Silicon mold built to fabricate the microfluidic devices.

In Figure 3, a PDMS device is shown, before and after being bonded to the glass microscope slide following this process.

Figure 3. View of a PDMS microfluidic device: (a) before plasma treatment, and (b) after plasma treatment, already bonded to the microscope slide.

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Experimental results obtained with the microfluidics devices and by micropipette aspiration

3.1 Cells used in the experiments

In this work, ARPE-19 cells were used to validate the developed technology. This is a commercial retinal pigment epithelial cell line derived from a 19-year-old male who died in a traffic accident. The cells were provided by the Biomaterials and Regenerative Engineering Laboratory at CTB-UPM.

The cells were cultured in DMEM/F-12 medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% penicillin-streptomycin (Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 37°C with 5% CO₂ in a 100 mm culture dish. Cell passages were performed weekly (every 5–7 days) when cultures reached 80% confluence, under a laminar flow hood with sterile materials. The first step in this process was to remove the culture medium and wash the cells with PBS. Once the PBS was removed, 1 mL of 0.05% trypsin-EDTA (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was added. The cells were then incubated at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 15 minutes. After incubation, trypsin was deactivated by adding DMEM/F-12 medium with 10% FBS at a 1:4 ratio.

Using a micropipette, the cells were detached from the culture plate and transferred to a Falcon tube, which was centrifuged (ROTINA-380R, Hettich) for 5 minutes at 1500 RPM and 21°C. After centrifugation, the presence of a cell pellet was verified, and the supernatant was discarded. The cells were resuspended in DMEM/F-12 medium with 10% FBS. Using a 20–200 µL micropipette and a Neubauer chamber, the cells were counted. Finally, the cells were returned to the incubator, with a portion used for experiments (approximately 4–5 × 10⁵ cells per experiment) and the remainder maintained to sustain the cell line.

Additionally, experiments were performed with fixed cells, following the protocol from Miltenyi Biotec [37]. First, cells were fixed by adding 250 µL of Inside Fix (Miltenyi Biotec) per 1 mL of suspension containing 10⁶ cells. After mixing, the cells were incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature (~27°C in the culture room). Next, the cells were centrifuged for 5 minutes at 500 × g at 4°C, and the supernatant was discarded. Finally, the cell pellet was resuspended in a PBS-based buffer (autoMACS® Rinsing Solution).

3.2 Results obtained with the microfluidics devices

We have used the methodology developed in this work to measure the mechanical properties of fixed cells in constrictions with two different width values. Experiments with fixed cells were carried out using 5 µm and 10 µm devices to compare their behavior. The analysis of the experiments was done as described in our previous work [1]. The values of the Young's modulus were recorded for each cell. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of the Young's modulus for fixed cells passing through 5 μm and 10 μm constrictions.

Width of the constriction (μm)	Estimated Young's modulus (Pa) of individual cells	Average value of the Young's modulus \pm standard error (kPa)
10	8613, 14865, 6219, 5462, 5698, 4716	7.6 ± 1.6
5	13962, 19302, 21290, 20089, 29342	20.8 ± 2.3

3.2 Results obtained by micropipette aspiration

Micropipette aspiration is a classical technique in the field of mechanobiology and later developed for mechanical experiments. The method employs a micrometer-sized capillary with an inner diameter smaller than that of the sample to be aspirated. For aspiration to occur, a pressure difference must be created between the sample and the interior of the micropipette. This is typically achieved by using an adjustable water reservoir, which generates a suction pressure that draws the sample into the capillary. Once the capillary and the sample are in contact, the sample undergoes deformation as it is drawn inside. The mechanical behavior of the specimen can then be evaluated by analyzing its geometry within the capillary as a function of the suction pressure, using an appropriate mechanical model to interpret the experimental data [4,5].

Figure 4. Schematic of the experimental setup used to simultaneously adjust the pressure difference (ΔP), temperature, and position of the capillary. On the right, images captured during the test are shown, where the progression of a cell inside the capillary can be observed [5].

For this work, microcapillaries with diameters of 10 μm and 5 μm were used. The capillaries were made of glass and manufactured by BioMedical Instruments (Germany). To observe the samples, an inverted optical microscope (Meiji TECHNO TC5400, Saitama, Japan) was used. Figure 4 schematically represents the setup of a micropipette aspiration test.

The aspiration experiments were performed by increasing the aspiration pressure ΔP at a rate of 10 Pa/s. The experiments have been analysed using the linearized version developed by Plaza et al. [4] of the equation obtained by Zhou et al. [6]. The values of the Young's modulus were recorded for each cell. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Values of the Young's modulus for fixed cells by using microcapillaries with diameters of 5 μm and 10 μm .

Diameter of the microcapillary (μm)	Estimated Young's modulus (Pa) of individual cells	Average value of the Young's modulus \pm standard error (kPa)
10	5109, 3396, 4861, 14008, 2041, 2040, 1041, 1430, 885, 719	3.6 ± 1.3
5	3672, 5607, 6487, 4397, 4845, 4839, 3672, 5918, 11655, 3789,	2.4 ± 0.8

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Comparison of the results and discussion

The first experimental results obtained in this work, showed in this report, provide evidence for various expected results. First, the deformation of the cells in the experiments in the microconstriction devices occurs very rapidly, the total duration of the passage of the cell through the constriction is of the order of tenths of seconds, and the estimated value of the Young's modulus corresponds to the *instantaneous* deformation of the cell. However, the experiments in the micropipette aspiration experiments are performed at a lower speed. The total duration of the experiment is of the order of minutes. Therefore, as expected for a viscoelastic material, the measured Young's modulus should be higher in the microfluidics devices. Roughly, the measured Young's modulus by the microfluidics device is one order of magnitude larger than the value obtained by micropipette aspiration. Second, with both techniques, there is an important variability of the measured values, as usually occurs for cells, due to the irregular shape and the inhomogeneity.

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Conclusions and future work

This deliverable shows the first results of the measurements of the Young's modulus of fixed cells in the microfluidics devices. These results are compared with those obtained by micropipette aspiration. The results obtained with both techniques show variability and differences between both techniques which are in agreement with the properties of an inhomogeneous and viscoelastic material.

These first encouraging results with this reference material provide a basis to continue this experimental work, to complete the measurements with larger samples.

At this moment, the methodology to carry out the experiments is completely developed and it is possible to perform experiments with cell lines of interest. Various cell lines are being considered presently and the results will be included in future deliverables.

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